

Reaction Thrust Without Mass Expulsion Using Arcs That Exchange the Velocity of Rotating Weights

We are a group of nine people. In October 2025, we filed a patent application for this invention (see figures), and we had a prototype built (see photos). For reasons that are not relevant here, it was not possible to test it. (There must be a reason why flying saucers have that particular shape and size: to achieve the required power).

Regardless of the laws of physics, we would like to clarify that the operation of this invention is based on the “magic” of rotation.

For proper operation, it would be better to modify the mechanism shown in the photos. Let us assume there are two weights, each with its own rotating arm, with each weight positioned at the center of its own arc. The arc should be long, slightly more or slightly less than half a circumference.

In the movement of the arcs, there should be a stop to prevent them from exceeding their limits. The remaining portions of the arcs should overlap in such a way that they can repel each other magnetically or electromagnetically.

Consider a weight with its arc mounted on the circumference and rotating with its arm. When this weight is near the lower part of the figure, it receives an electromagnetic push from the fixed structure toward the left through a point on its arc. Consequently, by reaction, the mechanism receives a push toward the right.

(Then, during the first quarter-turn, the centrifugal and centripetal forces should compensate for the push, and during the second quarter-turn there is another push that should act like a rebound.)

However, since the weights rotate together with their respective arcs, before the weight has traveled along the left side, it transfers its higher rotational speed to its twin weight through the arcs. As a result, there will be little centrifugal and centripetal effect on the left side.

Indeed, we believe that the centrifugal and centripetal effects have had little time to act on the left side of the circumference because the first weight was located around the first 30° of the first quarter-turn, while the twin weight was located around the last 30° of the second quarter-turn.

In practice, the first weight has lost speed, while the twin weight has become excessively fast and can be slowed down electromagnetically by the non-rotating part when it is around the first 30° of the third quarter-turn. In this way, the mechanism receives a second push toward the right.

Then there is a greater centrifugal push toward the right because the weight still has a higher speed than the weight on the left side.

At this point, the weights exchange roles. The former twin weight becomes the first weight and, when it reaches the lower part of the figure—that is, around the last 30° of the fourth quarter-turn—it receives an electromagnetic push toward the left through a point on its arc. Consequently, by reaction, the mechanism receives a push toward the right, and the second half-turn begins.

In our opinion, this occurs—and cannot occur otherwise—because a mechanism constructed in this way must necessarily generate an internal thrust.

We would appreciate any feedback, and perhaps even some suggestions.

